

Thermo-Physical Properties of CaO-Fe₂O₃ Binary Mixture and its Application in the Field of Nuclear Reactor as Simulant Material

Sunil Kumar Jatav, Vijay Kumar Pandey, U. Pandel, A. K. Nayak, Rajendra Kumar Duchaniya

Abstract: *The simulant materials play important role in the melt coolability experiments to understand the actual scenarios of core melt accidents in the field of nuclear reactor. Simulant materials are generally oxide/ceramics materials which have the properties similar to the properties of corium (mixture of UO₂, ZrO₂, Zr alloy, Fe, Ni and Cr etc.). This work was carried out to determine the thermo-physical properties of CaO-Fe₂O₃ binary mixtures of different ratio of CaO and Fe₂O₃ (23C77F, 26C74F, 29C71F, 32C68F and 35C65F; here the ratio is in the wt% and C for CaO and F for Fe₂O₃) and compare the properties of CaO-Fe₂O₃ with the properties of corium. It was observed that the thermo-physical properties of CaO-Fe₂O₃ binary mixture are close to the properties of corium, so it can be said that this material is simulant material. In this research work, thermal behavior of CaO-Fe₂O₃ was also carried out using differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). The simulant material CaO-Fe₂O₃ can be used in the melt coolability experiment to understand the phenomena that happened during the core melt accidents in the nuclear reactor.*

Keywords: *simulant materials, melt-coolability, corium, CaO-Fe₂O₃ binary mixture, thermo-physical properties.*

I. INTRODUCTION

The nuclear industry plays an important role in the energy production. The nuclear industry adopts advanced techniques to avoid any type of incidents, but the severe accidents is major threat when it happens. The multiple safety system fails and leads to the melting of reactor core during the severe accidents. The reactor core melts and relocated at the lower head of in-vessel. If it is not cooled at time, the molten mass attack the wall of the in-vessel due to the unavailability of coolant. The molten mass released in to ex-vessel with high amount of coolant and lead to the generation of steam that increases the pressure and may lead to steam explosion.

The various techniques are used to mitigate and termination of the severe accident. The melt-coolability experiments are used to understand the phenomena of core melt accidents. The three types of quenching techniques are used in the melt-coolability experiments namely, top

flooding, indirect cooling and bottom flooding [1]. In the melt-coolability experiments, simulant materials are used to simulate the phenomena that are occurred in the nuclear reactor during core melt accidents. The ceramics/glass type materials such as sodium borosilicate glass, CaO-B₂O₃, CaO-TiO₂, Bi₂O₃-TiO₂ and CaO-WO₂ etc. were used in the past melt coolability experiments [2-5]. The simulant material is the material which have the thermo-physical properties similar or close to the properties of corium. Corium is the mixtures of materials issued from the molten core at very high temperature. The corium consists of UO₂, ZrO₂, Zr, and in small amounts of Ni, Cr, Ag, Fe, In, Cd [6]. The complex physical and chemical phenomena took place during the nuclear severe accident. To simulate these phenomena, various types of simulant material has been used in the previous research. Low temperature simulant material used by CORIME [7], Scaled Simulant Spreading Experiments (S3C) [8], and BALI [9-10] due to lower costs and constraints. Some experiment like KATS [11] or COMET facilities [12], used high temperature simulant materials (alumina and thermite) to simulate real corium phenomena. CEA [13] has taken a large program on severe accident with using prototypic corium. The prototypic simulant material has also been used in past research in the experiments like COMAS [14], FARO-KROTOS [15], MACE [16], and COTELS [17]. So, simulant material (non-prototypic and Prototypic) are used to understand the real phenomena by melt coolability experiments during the core melt accidents.

In this research work, the thermo-physical properties (melting point, density, specific heat capacity, thermal conductivity, thermal diffusivity and heat of fusion) of CaO-Fe₂O₃ binary mixture with various ratio by wt.% (23C77F, 26C74F, 29C71F, 32C68F and 35C65F) was calculated. The powder of CaO and Fe₂O₃ was mixed in mortar and pestle for 35-40 minutes. Then, the mixed material was characterized with differential scanning calorimetry. The melting point, heat of fusion and specific heat capacity of CaO-Fe₂O₃ binary mixture was determined using the DSC data. The thermal conductivity and density were calculated by using the mixture rule. The thermal diffusivity was calculated using the thermal conductivity, density and specific heat capacity values of CaO-Fe₂O₃. All the thermo-physical properties of CaO-Fe₂O₃ binary mixture were observed close to the properties of corium. So, the CaO-Fe₂O₃ binary mixture can be used in the melt coolability experiments to simulate the scenario of severe accident.

Revised Manuscript Received on February 06, 2020.

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II. MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

The CaO and Fe₂O₃ powders were mixed in the mortar and pestle and prepared five sample using various ratio of CaO and Fe₂O₃ (by wt.%) (23C77F, 26C74F, 29C71F, 32C68F and 35C65F; here, C for CaO and F for Fe₂O₃). Thermal behavior was determined of these powder mixtures by using differential scanning calorimetry. The DSC experiments was performed in the temperature range from room temperature to 1350°C with 10°C/minute heating rate in the nitrogen atmosphere. The weight of samples was taken 10 mg (for each sample) in the DSC experiments. The melting point, heat of fusion and specific heat capacity was determined using the DSC data. The formula [18] was used to calculate the specific heat capacity (C_p) was given below as

$$C_p = \frac{Q}{m \cdot \Delta T} \quad \dots (1)$$

Where, Q is the amount of heat required to increase the temperature the material, m is amount of material and ΔT is the temperature difference.

The density of CaO-Fe₂O₃ was calculated using following formulae (Gross et al. and Hirai formulae) [19].

$$\rho = \frac{x_{CaO} \cdot M_{CaO} + (1 - x_{CaO}) \cdot M_{Fe_2O_3}}{\left(\frac{x_{CaO} \cdot M_{CaO}}{\rho_{CaO}}\right) + \left(\frac{(1 - x_{CaO}) \cdot M_{Fe_2O_3}}{\rho_{Fe_2O_3}}\right)} \quad \dots (2)$$

Where, ρ = density of CaO-Fe₂O₃, kg/m³,
 x_{CaO} = mole fraction of CaO,
 $x_{Fe_2O_3}$ = mole fraction of Fe₂O₃,
 ρ_{CaO} = density of CaO, kg/m³,
 $\rho_{Fe_2O_3}$ = density of Fe₂O₃, kg/m³,
 M_{CaO} = molecular mass of CaO,
 $M_{Fe_2O_3}$ = molecular mass of Fe₂O₃

El-Fakharany et al., (2012) has reported the thermal conductivity of CaO approximate 1.5 W/mK [20] and Takeda et al., (2009) has reported the thermal conductivity of Fe₂O₃ approximate 3 W/mK [21]. the thermal conductivity of CaO-Fe₂O₃ was calculated using Gross et al. and Hirai formulae that is given below [19].

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Thermal conductivity, } k & \\ &= x_{CaO} \cdot k_{CaO} + x_{Fe_2O_3} \cdot k_{Fe_2O_3} \\ &- 0.72(x_{CaO} \cdot x_{Fe_2O_3}) \end{aligned}$$

Where, k = thermal conductivity, W/mK,
 k_{CaO} = thermal conductivity of CaO, W/mK,
 $k_{Fe_2O_3}$ = thermal conductivity of Fe₂O₃, W/mK,
 x_{CaO} = mole fraction of CaO,
 $x_{Fe_2O_3}$ = mole fraction of Fe₂O₃,
 The thermal diffusivity of CaO-Fe₂O₃ (26:74 by wt.%) was calculated using the following equation. [20]

$$\alpha = k / (\rho \cdot C_p)$$

Where, α = thermal diffusivity, m²/s,
 ρ = density, kg/m³,
 C_p = Specific heat capacity, J/kg.K,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Thermal conductivity, } k & \\ &= x_{CaO} \cdot k_{CaO} + x_{Fe_2O_3} \cdot k_{Fe_2O_3} \\ &- 0.72(x_{CaO} \cdot x_{Fe_2O_3}) |k_{CaO} - k_{Fe_2O_3}| \end{aligned}$$

... (3)

Where, k = thermal conductivity, W/mK, k_{CaO} = thermal conductivity of CaO, W/mK, $k_{Fe_2O_3}$ = thermal conductivity of Fe₂O₃, W/mK, x_{CaO} = mole fraction of CaO, $x_{Fe_2O_3}$ = mole fraction of Fe₂O₃.

The thermal diffusivity of CaO-Fe₂O₃ was calculated using the following equation [22].

$$\alpha = k / (\rho \cdot C_p) \quad \dots (4)$$

Where, α = thermal diffusivity, m²/s,
 ρ = density, kg/m³,
 C_p = Specific heat capacity, J/kg.K,

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The study of thermal behavior of CaO-Fe₂O₃ with different composition was carried by using the differential scanning calorimetry as shown in figure 1. The five sample of CaO-Fe₂O₃ of different composition was study using the differential scanning calorimetry. the melting point of CaO-Fe₂O₃ mixture was increased with increasing the ratio of CaO and decreasing the ratio of Fe₂O₃. The sample 23CaO-77Fe₂O₃ (by wt.%) have shown the melting point around the 1212°C and the melting point of 35CaO-65Fe₂O₃ (by wt.%) was observed around 1218°C. The melting point of 29CaO-71Fe₂O₃(by wt.%) was observed around 1214°C. The variation in the melting point was observed more or less same. There is not much difference in the melting point peak. These peaks are peak where melting of material was started. The material was taken much heat to complete melting with increasing the amount of CaO and decreasing the amount of Fe₂O₃.

The heat of fusion was increased with increasing the ratio of CaO in the CaO-Fe₂O₃ binary mixture. The heat of fusion of the material is area under the melting peak in the DSC curve. It is confirmed from the figure 1 that the area under the melting peak was increased with increasing the ratio of CaO powder, so heat of fusion of the material was increased. The heat of fusion of 23CaO-77Fe₂O₃ (by wt.%), 26CaO-74Fe₂O₃ (by wt.%), 29CaO-71Fe₂O₃ (by wt.%), 32CaO-68Fe₂O₃ (by wt.%) and 35CaO-65Fe₂O₃ (by wt.%) was found around 101 J/g, 104 J/g, 119 J/g, 133 J/g, and 157 J/g, respectively, as shown in the table 1.

The specific heat capacity of 23CaO-77Fe₂O₃ (by wt.%), 26CaO-74Fe₂O₃ (by wt.%), 29CaO-71Fe₂O₃ (by wt.%), 32CaO-68Fe₂O₃ (by wt.%) and 35CaO-65Fe₂O₃ (by wt.%) was also calculated by using equation (1) and DSC results and specific heat capacity was found around 974 J/kg.K, 1565 J/kg.K, 956 J/kg.K, 1460 J/kg.K, and 821 J/kg.K, respectively, as shown in the table 1. The specific heat capacity is heat that was absorbed by the material to increase 1°C temperature of 1 gram of material.

Figure 1. DSC curves for various composition of CaO-Fe₂O₃ binary mixture.

The density of the material was calculated using the equation (2). The density of CaO and Fe₂O₃ are 3.34 g/cm³ and 5.24 g/cm³, respectively. These values of density of CaO and Fe₂O₃ was used in the equation (2) to calculate the density of CaO-Fe₂O₃. The density of CaO-Fe₂O₃ was increased with increasing the amount of CaO, as shown in the table 1.

The thermal conductivity of CaO-Fe₂O₃ was calculated using the equation (3). Values of thermal conductivity of CaO and Fe₂O₃ was used to calculate the thermal conductivity of CaO-Fe₂O₃ mixture. The thermal conductivity of CaO-Fe₂O₃ was varied with the variation in composition of CaO and Fe₂O₃. The thermal conductivity of CaO-Fe₂O₃ was shown in the table 1. The thermal conductivity of this material decreased with increasing the ratio of CaO. The thermal conductivity of this material is very close to the thermal conductivity of corium.

The thermal diffusivity of CaO-Fe₂O₃ was also calculated theoretically using the equation (4). For the calculation of thermal diffusivity, values of density, specific heat capacity and thermal conductivity was used. The thermal diffusivity of CaO-Fe₂O₃ was observed close to thermal diffusivity of corium as shown in the table 1.

All the thermo-physical properties (melting point, density, specific heat capacity, thermal conductivity and thermal diffusivity) of CaO-Fe₂O₃ with different composition of CaO and Fe₂O₃ are close the properties of Corium [4, 23] and other simulant material CaO-B₂O₃ [4], sodium borosilicate glass [24] that were used in the past research of melt coolability. These thermo-physical properties of CaO-Fe₂O₃ was shown in table 1. The properties of CaO-Fe₂O₃ are more or less same for all the composition of CaO-Fe₂O₃ binary mixute. The material CaO-Fe₂O₃ is non-toxic, easily available, economical and easy to use at laboratory basis, so it can be used in the melt coolability experiments to simulate the actual melt coolability phenomena that occurs in the nuclear reactor during the core melt accidents or nuclear severe accidents.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The thermo-physical properties of CaO-Fe₂O₃ with different composition was carried out in this research work. The melting point, heat of fusion, and specific heat capacity of CaO-Fe₂O₃ were determined using differential scanning calorimetry. The density, thermal conductivity and thermal

diffusivity were determined theoretically using mixture rule. All these thermo-physical properties were altered with increasing the ratio of CaO in the mixture of CaO and Fe₂O₃. These thermo-physical properties of CaO-Fe₂O₃ for all the composition that was used in present research work was observed more or less same and close to the properties of corium and other simulant material that was used in past research work. The material CaO-Fe₂O₃ binary mixture is also very useful to simulate the actual melt coolability phenomena of core melt accidents that were occurred in the nuclear reactor and it is a simulant material as corium.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

I am very grateful of Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Mumbai because the experimental facility is established of its help in the Department of Metallurgical and Materials Engineering, Malaviya National Institute of Technology Jaipur. I am working on the BARC funded project entitled "Quenching Behavior of Bottom Flooded Molten Pool" as a Senior Research Fellow.

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Table- I: Thermo-physical properties of CaO-Fe₂O₃ with respect to the properties of corium.

Properties	23C77F	26C74F	29C71F	32C68F	35C65F	Corium (UO ₂ + ZrO ₃ mixture) (80:20 by weight)
Density (kg/m ³)	4639	4571	4499	4424	4365	7450
Melting Point (°C)	1212	1215	1214	1215	1218	2577
Specific heat capacity (J/kg.K)	974	1565	956	1460	821	410
Heat of fusion (J/g)	101	104	119	133	157	----
Thermal conductivity (W/m.K)	2.04	1.98	1.92	1.87	1.82	2.5
Thermal diffusivity (m ² /s)	4.51×10 ⁻⁷	2.77×10 ⁻⁷	4.46×10 ⁻⁷	2.89×10 ⁻⁷	5.10×10 ⁻⁷	8.18×10 ⁻⁷